

Additional file 2: List of ambulatory care-sensitive condition

Stroke
Angina
Heart failure
High blood pressure
Bronchitis
Mental or behavioural disorders due to substance abuse
Depression
Back pain
Diarrhoea
Flu
Ear, nose, and throat infections
Diabetes
Epilepsy
Sleeping problems
Cavities